

Festivals and cultural preservation: An analysis of '*Aoleang*' amongst the Konyak Nagas

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Human civilizations across various indigenous communities and caste groups have always celebrated various festivals. Festivals are crucial to solve social conflicts and maintain social order and solidarity. Festivals use tangible and intangible aspects of culture to assert the identity of the community. The paper critically analyses the *Aoleang* festival of the Konyak Nagas of eastern part of Nagaland. Konyak Nagas are a community with traditional hereditary chief or *Anghs*. Konyak Nagas are an agricultural community and *Aoleang* is a post-harvest festival. Earlier *Aoleang* happened at different times of the year for different villages or different *Angh* (*chief*) territory based on the insights of the elders. However, after conversion to Christianity and independence, the State government of Nagaland has fixed the dates of *Aoleang*. The festival starts on 1st of April and ends on 6th April. The festival has now turned from a post-harvest festival to be celebrated at different points in time to a calendar event of the government with fixed dates. The paper will therefore draw out the significance of *Aoleang* amongst the Konyak Nagas and delineate how the various crafts, rituals, dresses and *morungs* (traditional boys dormitory), serve as a mechanism to preserve the traditional knowledge of the Konyak Nagas.

Keywords: Harvest festival, traditional knowledge, rituals, *morungs*.